

UNRAVELLING THE ACCEPTABILITY AND DIFFICULTY OF THE SCIENCE TECHNOLOGY ENGINEERING AND MATHEMATICS STUDENTS IN LAMBAYONG NATIONAL HIGH SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

An abundant number of cases caught society's attention when college students who graduated in the STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) strands started choosing a non-STEM field as their major when they enrolled in college. The study aimed to explore and gain an in-depth understanding of the unraveling the acceptability and difficulty of the science technology engineering and mathematics students in Lambayong National High School. This research used qualitative research which is a research approach that allows the researcher to interpret the life of people to understand their problems better and deeper to generate solutions that are relevant to their situations. The participants of the study are 11 senior high school STEM students in Lambayong National High School for the school year 2022-2023. A semi-structured guide survey questionnaire was used to collect the necessary information and responses from the participants of the study. Thematic analysis was used to process the responses of the participants. On the aspiration of students enrolling in the STEM track the following themes were generated upon the analysis of the responses such as Nurture Knowledge and a lot of opportunities. On the challenges faced by STEM students regarding subject lessons, projects, and requirements submitted the following themes that were generated based on the responses of the student participants, Loaded with requirements and complex scientific concepts. Interestingly, the generated theme from the student participants was Time management.

Keywords: *STEM, Acceptability, Difficulty, Lambayong, Philippines*

INTRODUCTION

Quality education is the heart of sustainable development and a powerful catalyst for developing more just, humane, and equitable societies Department of Education (Philippines) (2016).

Quality education has become critical in many countries that are expanding enrolments rapidly to achieve Education for All, UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) (2017).

The Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) track of the Philippine K to 12- Enhanced Basic Education Curriculum is designed to produce graduates of secondary level who will take science, research, mathematics, and engineering-related courses in tertiary level and thereby add to the scientific and scholarly workforce of the country, DepEd (2014). It can be noted that Magno, (2010) said that a curriculum that is purposely designed for mathematics and science-inclined students could be the answer to a decade-long problem of a low number of mathematics and science practitioners in the country.

Republic Act 10533 otherwise known as the Enhanced Basic Education Act of 2013 mandates the Department of Education to create another level of basic education composed of two years. These two additional years in the secondary level shall comprise the senior high school program as set by the aforementioned law.

The primary goal of the program is to prepare secondary students to master the prerequisite skills needed in professional courses for those who prefer academic tracks and to equip them with employment and industrial skills needed for those who prefer technical-vocational and other tracks. Braza, 2014, mentioned that the new curriculum was the response of the government to the call of educators for the standardization of the country's educational system to comply with international standards.

Nevertheless, in the early stages of the implementation of the K to 12 curriculum, several oppositions to the program arose. This prompted the researchers to study the acceptability and difficulty of Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics among students at Lambayong National High School. Since there are students who want to shift from STEM to another academic strand.

Research Questions

The study focuses on the experiences, challenges, and coping mechanisms of STEM students in Lambayong National High School.

Specifically, the study sought to carried out with the following objectives;

1. What is the aspiration of students in enrolling in STEM track.

2. What are the challenges faced by STEM students regarding subject lessons, projects, and requirements submitted?
3. Narrate their coping mechanism to address those challenges they experienced.
4. What school program may be crafted based on the result of the study?

METHODOLOGY

This investigation employed a phenomenological research design as it can study people's experiences, how people construct meaning in their lives, and commonalities that transverse individuals experiencing a specific phenomenon (Edmonds & Kennedy, 2017). Notably, this study utilized Transcendental phenomenology, which aimed to seek understanding in human experience, which is performed by laying aside prepossessed ideas to view the phenomena to be investigated through a new lens, allowing it to immerge, giving its distinct meaning and form.

The focus participants of this study are ten (10) STEM senior high students who were selected through purposive sampling. This phenomenological study selected participants that fit the suggestion of Creswell (2014) as an ample number of participants to generate meaningful themes and valuable interpretations.

RESULTS

On the perceived freezing issues faced by senior high schools in Lambayong Municipality in offering the STEM strand. The following themes were Lack of facilities and equipment and lack of competent and qualified teachers.

On the issues and concerns of secondary schools on the offering of Science Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Strand, the themes generated Human resources and equipment

Interestingly, On the possible plans of the school in offering Science Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics Strand following themes were Improve school facilities and capacitate teachers.

DISCUSSION

On the aspiration of students enrolling in the STEM track the following themes were generated upon the analysis of the responses such as **a. Nurture Knowledge and b. a lot of opportunities.**

The first theme that was generated was **nurture knowledge**. Students believed that they would be one step higher with other academic tracks. In terms of their aspiration why they tend to enroll STEM track in senior high school because they believe that they

will nurture their knowledge in the subjects offered in STEM classes, as the participants share their aspirations as follows;

“I choose STEM because It is related to the course that I want, getting this strand will nurture my knowledge more. Choosing this will improve and will make my understanding broader which will help me in getting the course that I want”. **Participant 1, Male;**

“I chose the STEM track because it is related to the course that I want to take in college. I hope STEM can help me expand my knowledge, to easily understand everything that I need in the field that I want to take someday”. **PARTICIPANT 5, Female;**

“I chose the academic track STEM because I want to take a medicine course in college. This would be a good preparation to nurture my knowledge in Science”. **PARTICIPANT 9, Male;**

The second theme that was generated was, **a lot of opportunities** as STEM believes that taking up the STEM strand has a lot of opportunities in the future.

In response to numerous calls for more rigorous STEM (science, technology, engineering, and mathematics) education to improve US competitiveness and the job prospects of next-generation workers, especially those from low-income and minority groups, a growing number of schools emphasized.

As STEM as the student participants share their thoughts as;

“I chose the STEM strand because there are a lot of opportunities in this strand like scholarships, etc. and I want to improve myself more in mathematics”. **PARTICIPANT 3, Male;**

“I chose the STEM strand because they say that, it has many opportunities in the future, and one of the goals is to be a successful person in the future”. **PARTICIPANT 4, Male;**

Lastly student shared; *“I am motivated to choose the STEM track by my family and friends. My aspiration and goal through my enrolment in this field is to learn and be ready for my college journey and also to be on the honors list for my parents to be proud of me”.* **PARTICIPANT 8, Male**

The result of the analysis is in line with the global context where education is recognized as, a basic human right and the foundation on which to build peace and drive sustainable development (the United Nations Educational Social and Cultural Organization (UNESCO) may be regarded as important work. We live in times ‘characterized by a new explosion of scientific knowledge’ and Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) education is considered an important factor for strong economic and social futures (Organization for Education Co-operation and Development (OECD), United Nations Educational Social and Cultural Organization (UNESCO). STEM learning can promote important possibilities for building knowledge across disciplines and incorporates.

On the challenges faced by STEM students regarding subject lessons, projects, and requirements submitted

Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics, abbreviated as STEM, is a promising field with increasing popularity due to its benefits in the modern world of globalization and modernization. Science and mathematics are the basics of the technological developments going on in the world. Thus, the children should be motivated to learn STEM from early school days. The minds of small kids are like a sponge, and they can grasp everything quickly. STEM education should be encouraged from childhood so that children like it and continue with it for higher education Ampartzaki, M., Kalogiannakis, M., & Papadakis, S. (2021).

On the challenges faced by STEM students regarding subject lessons, projects, and requirements submitted the following themes that were generated based on the responses of the student participants **a. Loaded with requirements and b. complex scientific concepts**

The first theme that was generated was **loaded with requirements** Students as mandated to pass their requirements as one of the criteria to solve their grades, but it was noted that reading and analyzing their responses loaded with requirements was once the challenges they faced.

As the student participants shared their experiences on the challenges they faced as;

“Loaded requirements. The most common difficulty that I find is in solving math equations”. **Participant 1, Male;**

“I think the hurdles or difficulties that STEM students experience is navigating through mathematical problem-solving because sometimes we can't easily understand or catch up with the given”. **PARTICIPANT 2, Male;**

“The hardest difficulties and challenges I faced in the STEM strand were having overload requirements and not having enough time during the examinations and quizzes for the mathematics subject”. **PARTICIPANT 8, Male**

Looking into the challenge of STEM students, still education is the backbone of any country for its economic and social development. Science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) education and skills are required for tough analytical problem-solving and supporting job functions. National Science Board (2014) has researched employment prospects and found that major broad occupation exists in the science and engineering categories.

The second generated theme from the student participants was **complex scientific concepts**, they are facing just challenges in taking up STEM in senior high school.

We are in the process of transitioning from the digital revolution, or the information age, to the age of synthesis (Cai, 2011). We argue that teaching and learning in the age

of synthesis targets new domains of expertise: evaluating and applying seemingly disparate information, accommodating the accelerated emergence of new knowledge and sophisticated technologies, preparing for transdisciplinary careers, and merging traditional disciplines to better meet the needs of citizens in the 21st century.

On the challenges faced by the senior high school STEM student on complex scientific concepts, they shared their thoughts about this matter;

“Stress and lack of sleep are some of the most common difficulties STEM students face while navigating through complex scientific concepts or mathematical problem-solving”. **PARTICIPANT 7, Male;**

“The challenges faced by STEM students are time management for all the projects required by numerous subject teachers and memorizing the formulas for General Mathematics and Pre-Calculus”. **PARTICIPANT 9, Male;**

“Solving Math problems is the most common weakness for us students. But we are learning and improving”. **PARTICIPANT 10, Male;**

“Challenges faced by STEM students are time managing all the requirements in each subject and also in problem-solving you have to memorize all formulas and understand each concept”. **PARTICIPANT 11, Female**

On the coping mechanism of the STEM senior high school participants to address those challenges they experienced

Several research projects in educational assessment reveal that students struggle when it comes to accomplishing problem-solving tasks in Mathematics. Such a struggle is primarily due to the complexities of problem-solving.

The generated theme from the student participants was **Time management**.

Time management is the process of consciously planning and controlling time spent on specific tasks to increase how efficient you are.

On the coping mechanism of STEM students, their coping mechanism for the challenges that they had encountered was Time Management.

As the student participants shared their experiences as'

“We typically manage our stress associated with the rigorous academic demands and workload by managing our time and doing all the work step by step”. **PARTICIPANT 2, Male;**

“Talking with my friends asking them about our lessons and ranting in our group chat. I have to balance my time for other extra activities”. **PARTICIPANT 4, Male;**

“We manage it by helping each other. I have to make sure that my time will be managed properly”. **PARTICIPANT 5, Female;**

“Stress- eating. That temporary feeling of jubilation boosts our state to do things that we should. I need to balance my time with other house chores”. **PARTICIPANT 6, Male;**

“Having some bonding sometimes is our way to manage our stress also having group activities inside the classroom such as games to release our stress”. **PARTICIPANT 7, Male;**

“I can manage the stress associated with the rigorous academic demands and workload in STEM by having time management and sometimes having fun, unwinding, and chilling”. **PARTICIPANT 8, Male;**

“Through time management and doing what we want on weekends”. **PARTICIPANT 9, Male**

Conclusions

The following conclusions are drawn based on the findings of the study.

Lack of facilities and equipment and lack of competent and qualified teachers are the common reasons why they are not offering STEM strands. To meet and to address the following freezing problems faced by the schools not offering STEM strands they need to Improve school facilities and capacitate teachers.

Recommendations

From the salient findings of this study and the conclusion reached, the following recommendations are presented;

1. The school heads may encourage Science and Mathematics teachers to undergo training in curriculum planning and implementation.
2. The Department of Education may provide technical assistance on the implementation of the STEM strand in schools that want to implement STEM strands.
3. The Department of Education may provide all the necessary facilities and equipment to the school to cater to STEM students.
4. Continuous retooling and professional development programs for STEM teachers must be sustained to align their pedagogy to the Generation Z students, and
5. Similar studies using other variables should be conducted to determine if the same results are obtained to confirm the conclusion that the extent of implementation of the STEM curriculum

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This paper has a single author and confirms the ethical standards.

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